

D8.3

Reports on Congress presentations M13

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→Communication, Dissemination &
Outreach

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→VUA

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General situation

Due to COVID-19 the Springschool of 2020, originally scheduled in March 2020, was first rescheduled to June 2020, but was eventually cancelled. Instead an online school was organised.

The team of WP 8, Communication and Dissemination, consisting of Philipp Rückriem and Simone Brannahl, Dissemination and Outreach Officers of PS Media, Berlin, and prof. dr. Thijl Sunier, Scientific Communication Officer of Vrije Universiteit, Amsterdam, prepared a number of documents and presentations for this school.

In general, we had to alter some formats and activities due to COVID-19, and we will continue to do so in the near future. Limited physical meetings with the ESR's will be possible provided travelling abroad is possible without lengthy quarantine periods.

Communication Activities

Jan-Aug

01/

January

Berlin Story Telling Workshop: 4 days Training how to tell a story, shoot and produce short reports and portraits, how to do an interview, how to shoot with an iPhone (FilmicPro App) and how to edit (Adobe Premiere Pro)

03→07/

March-July

Developing ideas for the ESRs individual webpages on MIDAs official website (content like podcasts, interactive web docs, graphics, animation etc.)

08/

August

Shooting of Social Network Analysis Workshop in Marburg

02/

February

Social Media Networks Campaign: everyday a picture and short introduction of each ESR on Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and itn- mida.org

06/

June

All 15 ESRs produced a 3 Minutes Video about their Presentation in Catania Spring School (Shooting & Editing)

First video production by the ESRs

In the run up to the School we asked the ESR's to prepare a short (3 minutes) video presentation as part of their assignment for the School.

PS MEDIA assisted and supported the editing process. It was the first time to edit a video for the majority of the ESRs.

The results will be published in Mid September in MIDAs social network channels.

Academic synergy

We started to set up a system to put together an online list of all relevant academic publications used by all the 15 projects.

By updating this list regularly, we will have an important document by the end of the MIDA project. In addition, there are several reading groups being organised by members of some of the ESR projects.

Although these activities are not directly related to the tasks of WP 8, we consider the spin-off important for the synergy within the MIDA-team, which is one of the aims of WP8.

Academic and non-academic output

During the School in June we presented our Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP).

The task of WP-8 is to coordinate dissemination and outreach activities of every ESR-team, for every thematic WP, and for MIDA as a whole, and to produce a coherent strategy to do so.

All ESR's are already busy learning how to do the public part and how to 'translate' their projects into a variety of forms and to communicate it to the different audiences. In addition, every ESR will produce and disseminate scientific knowledge. But these outputs or deliverables must be part of an overarching strategy and program.

We therefore developed ask each of the ESR-teams to provide a Dissemination and Communication Plan every 3 months. All DCP's together

provide the basic format for the outreach strategy of the whole MIDA-project. We consider this as a kind of ongoing update of dissemination activities (academic, professional, non-academic) to become visible in any of our online platforms. The 15 ESR supervising teams have a responsibility here in assisting their 'own' ESR in putting together this output.

We developed an online format for the DCP's (attached PDF) and we have asked the teams to start from the 1st of July 2020 with the 3-month DCP delivery. In the meantime, we have collected the first batch and we are now preparing a short report about the 1st DCP's.

DCP format example

ESR 5 Elmozafar Abdelhafiz (f. ex.)

WP__

DCP 07-2020

	Activities of the last 3 months	Planned Activities upcoming 3 months
Academic		
Professional / policy related		
Non-Academic		

Other activities/ ideas